

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation *Scholars' approach to language learning, teaching the language to learners in a quick and convenient way, the importance of modern methods in language learning, mastering communicative competence, actual active student learning-constructivist, combination of planned learning, developing student's communicative learning, applying knowledge to solve a particular problem, acquiring knowledge independently.*

Keywords: *innovative, multimedia, assignments, methodology, script, methods, communicative, constructive, role-playing, simulation, project, ability, DVDs, digital revolution, phonograph, broadcast, movie, tape recorder.*

Аннотация *Подход ученых к изучению языка, обучение языку учащихся быстрым и удобным способом, важность современных методов в изучении языка, овладение коммуникативной компетенцией, актуальное активное обучение-конструктивизм, сочетание планового обучения, развивающее коммуникативное обучение учащихся, применяя знания для решения конкретной задачи, самостоятельно приобретая знания.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационный, мультимедиа, задания, методология, сценарий, методы, коммуникатив, конструктив, ролевая игра, симуляция, проект, умение, DVD, цифровая революция, фонограф, трансляция, фильм, магнитофон.*

The XXI century is the century of new innovative technologies. Many people are very interested in learning

foreign languages, because in the computer age it is impossible not to know any foreign language. In

addition, Uzbeks have a proverb: “People who know the language know the nation”. By learning foreign languages and travelling people discover many differences in terms of culture, way of thinking, history, customs and lifestyles of other nations. Many modern methods of teaching language students in a convenient way have been developed by teachers. This paper discusses different approaches and techniques which can assist English language students to improve their learning skills by using technology. They teach in a unique way, depending on the student's ability to learn from these methods. I would like to draw your attention to some of these new innovative methods.

Modern educational technologies that are used to form the communicative competence of a schoolchild in learning another language are the most productive for creating an educational environment that provides a person-oriented interaction of all participants in the educational process. It is obvious that using any one technology of education,

no matter how perfect it is, will not create the most effective conditions for the disclosure and development of students' abilities and creativeness of a teacher.

In the past times, learning and teaching meant reading books, printing out handouts, face to face classes and doing assignments. Shortly, it was impossible to imagine lessons without a teacher, books and chalks. Today, education and training have taken on a whole new meaning. Computers are an essential part of every classroom and teachers are using DVDs, CD-ROMs and videos to show pupils how things work and operate. Pupils can *interact with the subject matters through the use of such web based tools and CD-ROMs*. Moreover, each pupil can progress at his/her own pace. Many researchers and projectors worked on this issue. One early example of a language learning simulation is the multimedia video disc program *A la rencontre de Philippe* developed by the Athena Language Learning Project at the M.I.T. Laboratory for Advanced Technology in the Humanities.

Philippe is a game for intermediate and advanced French learners that incorporates full motion video, sound, graphics, and text, allowing learners to "walk around" and explore simulated environments by following street signs or floor plans. To help language learners understand the sometimes challenging French, the program provides optional comprehension tools, such as a glossary and transcriptions of audio segments, as well as a video album that includes samples of language functions. Students can also create their own custom video albums, which they store on their own computer diskettes. According to Jeremy Harmer, "a word innovation means something new, which means new ideas to change things for better". He claims that "if we look at all the language teaching methods which are used all over the world by different teachers at different levels, we cannot say that all of them are 100% successful. Therefore, it is very important to keep looking and searching to find ways to make teaching and learning better".

According to Mudge, Multimedia

applied in English teaching may include four stages. The original stage can be dated back to the 1950s when only a few foreign language institutes started to employ phonograph, broadcast, movie, tape recorder and other current media in foreign language teaching. During that time, audio and video were once considered a significant revolution to the teaching of foreign language. Following in the 70s and 80s, audio and video developed dramatically with the advancement of electronic technology. Electronic taping, slide projectors, videocassette players, language labs and other electronic devices were included in this era. By the turn of ***90s, multimedia technology was becoming increasingly available in foreign language instruction because of the development of computer technology and the coming of the digital revolution.*** In the early 2000's, the internet became a powerful medium for the delivery of computer-aided learning materials. The internet provides a worldwide means to get information, lighten the work load, and communicate with each other at any

time and at any place. CALL which is Computer Assisted Language Learning came into play during the later part of the 20th century. Warschauer divided the history of CALL into three stages: behavioristic CALL, communicative CALL, and integrative CALL. Behavioristic CALL applied in 1960s and 1970s was based on the behaviorist learning and featured repetitive language drills. The computer was regarded as a mechanical tutor to deliver the materials to the pupils. An example of a behavioristic CALL strategy is PLATO [1; 168].

Communicative method. Learning content: texts should show conflicts that encourage the student to express their own opinions. Training is managed not through grammar, but is directed by communicative intentions (intentions). The student is in the center of learning. Language plane: the dominance of language production over language correctness, correctness, mistakes are made. Language becomes a means of communication. Exercises: exercises

of the communicative direction. Students learn “communication in the process of communication itself. Therefore, all the exercises and tasks must be communicatively justified by a lack of information, choice and reaction” [3; 150].

Constructivist method. Learning objective: the method is based on the actual active student learning. The task of the teacher is not to teach, but to contribute to the learning process. The lesson is action oriented. Educational content: proximity to reality of students, students are encouraged to independently construct their knowledge (for example, in the framework of project activities). Language plane: as wide as possible. Exercises: language production is at the heart of learning.

Script Method (story line method). This method is based on a combination of planned learning meanings for example, shopping goods sales with the interests and ideas of students. By receiving "impulses" from the teacher (the so-called key questions), students make their

contribution to the creation of history. This method does without textbooks. It is about creative planning, hypothesis selection, experiences, systematization and presentation of work. The designed story also contains elements from drama and role -playing. The teacher sets the framework for action and presents individual episodes. Pupils put their questions and find answers to them themselves.

Simulation method. Especially in the teaching of a foreign language to students of economic specialties of universities, one can successfully apply the method of simulations. In cybernetics, this term is used to model and simulate reality. The training deals with various simulation business games that provide students with the opportunity to develop their skills, apply knowledge to solve a particular problem in the so-called “safe environment” that imitates real situations, for example, in business, in work in a company. The simulation provides an opportunity for students to try themselves in a certain role the head, the president of the company,

gives the opportunity to explore the system of work of this enterprise. The participants in the game are given certain tasks to achieve a profit growth of the company, to conclude an agreement, to sell the company's shares, and so on. Simulations are characterized by a high degree of interest of the participants, the game is completely immersed, embodied in its role, and is sick of the result of the work, because the overall result of the game depends on the team spirit and speed of decision making. Thanks to the simulation, the skills of strategic planning of students are formed, the ability to work in a team, to negotiate, to convince a business partner is developed. Simulations streamline students' knowledge, prepare them for the need to make quick and motivated business decisions in their future activities. There are computer simulations, where participants work with a computer program, manage an imaginary company, and desktop simulations, where participants, companies, enterprises “exist” in the form of chips, maps.

Role play method. Role-playing is an active method of learning, a means of developing a student's communication skills. Role-playing game is associated with the interests of students, it is a means of emotional interest, motivation of learning activities. Role-playing is an active way of learning practical knowledge of a foreign language. Role-playing game helps to overcome the language barriers of students, significantly increases the amount of their speech practice. This is learning in action. There are a large number of forms, types of role-playing in foreign language lessons. For example, you can use the role-playing game "At the interview", where students take on the role of employer and employee. From all the above, it should be concluded that for the teacher today it is important to constantly improve their knowledge of foreign language teaching methods, introduce the latest educational concepts into their teaching practice, and keep up with the times.

Project method. Recently more and more teachers are using the project

methodology in the process of teaching a foreign language as one of the modern productive creative approaches that successfully implement the main objectives of teaching a foreign language in the formation of communicative and speech skills, which are necessary for students to communicate in a foreign language. The main purpose of the project method is to provide students with the opportunity acquiring knowledge independently in the process of solving practical tasks or problems that require the integration of knowledge from different subjects. If we talk about the method of projects as a pedagogical technology, this technology involves a set of research, searching, problematic methods, which are creative in nature. The teacher in the project is assigned as a developer, coordinator, expert and consultant. This technology contributes to the development of the creative abilities of students and develops their imagination and curiosity. During the preparation of projects, the creative and intellectual potential of student is revealed. The

method of projects teaches to conduct a research work, working in a team, conduct a discussion, solve problems [2; 240].

Come to the conclusion, the benefits of using new technologies in a language classroom can only be interpreted in terms of language learning objectives and changing conditions in society. The computer is a powerful tool for this process, as

international conversations often take place online. The main advantage of the new technologies is that they can be used to help prepare students for the increasingly demanding forms of international intercultural communication in order to succeed in their academic, professional and personal lives. It is no coincidence that it also aims to increase the learner's ability to learn the language easily.

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